

Pressure Dependent Solvent-induced Shifts in Molecular Vibrational Frequencies

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Solvent-induced vibrational frequency shifts are calculated for diatomic oscillators immersed in a solvent, using 'Hard-Fluid' model. This treatment is applied to homonuclear diatomic solutions, such as nitrogen, hydrogen, chlorine, etc. in different solvents such as carbon tetrachloride, methanol, toluene etc. in different packing fractions. The corresponding packing fractions are in the range 0.05–0.5. The repulsive and the attractive part of the molecular vibrational frequency shifts have been calculated. The repulsive contribution is calculated from the pair distribution function for hard-sphere cavities. The attractive part have been calculated from various solute parameters. The calculated results are compared with the experimental ones for certain cases and found to be satisfactory.

When a molecule in the gas phase is immersed in a typical solvent, its bonds are slightly stretched by a set attractive interaction with the solvent. The stretching becomes observable in downward shifts of vibrational frequencies of solute molecules. The vibrational frequency shifts induced by increasing pressure thus manifest the transition of the solute-solvent coupling from net attraction to net repulsion with increase in solvent density.

Several models have been proposed to treat this vibrational frequency shifts over a wide range of liquid densities. These models all invoke a net solvent-induced force that perturbs normal mode frequencies of an isolated solute molecule. For stretching vibrations frequency shift thus obtained are directly proportional to medium-induced changes in bond lengths. However, at present only the hard-sphere model formulated by Schweizer and Chandler¹ provides a direct evaluation of net solute-solvent interaction. This work presents a method to calculate this vibrational frequency shifts from the cavity distribution function^{2,3} and radial distribution function at near contact separation in mixed hard-sphere fluids³ of arbitrary composition and density. It provides a closed analytical form which can easily be incorporated into practical calculations. We have calculated the vibrational frequency shifts of pyridine in two different solvents to compare the experimental results and then calculated the same for N₂, Cl₂, H₂ in three different solvents.

Theory of calculations :

The prototype theoretical treatment of solvent-induced vibrational frequency shifts consider a diatomic oscillator immersed in various solvents. The net frequency shift, $\Delta\nu = \Delta\nu_R + \Delta\nu_A$, is the resultant of a positive contribution from repulsive component ($\Delta\nu_R$)^{1,4,5} and negative one from attractive part ($\Delta\nu_A$)^{1,6,7}.

Chart I. Equations for vibrational frequency shift.

Repulsive contribution :

$$F = F_{HS} \text{ and } G = G_{HS} = 0, \text{ evaluated at } r_{12} = r_e$$

$$F_{HS} = -KT[B_{12} + 3C_{12}r_e^2] \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\Delta\nu}{(n \leftarrow o)} \bigg/ \frac{\Delta\nu}{(n \leftarrow o)} = n(F/f) \left[-\frac{3}{2}(g/f) + G/F \right] \quad (2)$$

Attractive contribution :

$$\rho_o = \rho^* - \frac{p}{760} \frac{273.16}{T} \quad (3)$$

$$\Delta\nu_A = nC_A\rho_S \quad (4)$$

where, ρ_S is the density of the solvent, ρ^* the density of gas at 0°, g and f are cubic (anharmonic) and quadratic (harmonic) vibrational force constants, G and F the quadratic linear coefficient of meanforce potential, and C_A , B_{12} , C_{12} are mentioned in Table 1.

The hard-core diameters of the solutes and solvents were calculated from force constants⁸ and surface tension data⁹ respectively.

Results and Discussion

The values of solute and solvent parameters are presented in Tables 2 and 3.

The results of the calculated vibrational frequency shifts for different systems are given in Table 4. The shifts are more negative (downward shifts) at low pressure which raises to offset.

Equation (2) shows that frequency shift due to the interaction with the solvent is simply proportional to F , the first derivative of the repulsive contribution to the potential of mean force, exerted by the solvent on the solute with respect to r_{12} . As the solution is compressed, it will reduce the mean distance between molecules and this will enhance repulsive interactions as packing fraction increases.

The curves in Fig. 1, showing the variation of frequency shift with pressure, predict that frequency shifts are almost linear as in the behaviour expected in a continuum solvent upto a certain pressure range (≈ 2 K bar) but deviate from linearity and approaches to almost constant when the

TABLE 1—EQUATIONS FOR B_{12} , C_{12} AND C_A

$$B_{12} = \frac{1}{2} \sum \frac{\delta \ln Y_{ij}(r_{ij})}{\delta r_{ij}}$$

where, $\frac{\delta \ln Y_{ij}(r_{ij})}{\delta r_{ij}} = -n \delta_{ij} \sum_{K=1}^n \sigma_{ik}^2 \rho_k Y_{ik}(\sigma_{ik})$.

n is the number of components, δ_{ij} the Kroneker delta function and $\delta_{ij} = 1$ when $i = j$.

The value of Cavity distribution function at contact can be expressed as

$$Y_{ij}(\sigma_{ij}) = \frac{1}{1-\epsilon_3} + \frac{3\epsilon_2 S_{ij}}{(1-\epsilon_3)^2} + \frac{(\epsilon_2^2 S_{ij}^2)}{(1-\epsilon_3)^3}$$

where, $\epsilon_k = \left(\frac{\rho\pi}{6}\right) \sum_{i=1}^n X_i \sigma_i^k$; $S_{ij} = \frac{S_i S_j}{S_i + S_j}$

and $C = \frac{7-2\epsilon_3}{3}$

C_{12}

For homonuclear diatomics, C_{12} can be written as

$$C_{12} = \frac{\ln-\gamma\pi(\sigma_{11}) - \ln\gamma_{11}(o) - B_{11}(\sigma_{11})}{\sigma_{11}^3}$$

The expressions for $\ln \gamma_{11}(0)$ (Ref. 6).

C_A

$$C_A = -\frac{4\pi}{3} \frac{1}{\sigma_a^3} \left[\left(\frac{3}{2} I_a \frac{\delta\alpha_o}{\delta r} \Delta r \right) \alpha_s + \left(\frac{4}{3k_3 T} \mu_o \cdot \frac{\delta\mu_o}{\delta r} \cdot \Delta r \right) \mu_s^2 \right]$$

where $\sigma_a = \frac{1}{2} (\sigma_o + \sigma_s)$,

$$I_a = \frac{I_o I_s}{I_o + I_s} \text{ and } \Delta r = -\frac{3}{2} h C v_o g / f^2$$

Here, μ , α and I are the dipolemoments, polarisability and ionisation energy, o and s denote solute and solvent respectively, and Δr = change in bond length

TABLE 2—SOLUTE PARAMETERS

Solute	$f \times 10^{-5}$ dyne cm^{-1}	$-g \times 10^{-13}$ dyne cm^{-1}	r_e Å	I_o ev	v_o cm^{-1}	$\frac{\delta\alpha_o}{\delta r}$ Å ²	μ_o D	$\frac{\delta\mu_o}{\delta r}$ D cm^{-1}	σ_o Å	$\rho_o \times 10^{-20}$ cm^{-3}
N ₂	22.981	57 623	1.097 6	15 6	2 358.07	1.66	0	0	3.681	0.246 4
Cl ₂	3.233	45.565	1.987 5	11.5	559.71	2.02	0	0	4.155	0.250 1
H ₂	5.76	12.501	0.741 38	15 43	4 400.39	1.23	0	0	2.915	0.246 1

pressure is appreciable. This can qualitatively be explained by the fact that the shielding effects of the solvent cage increases with pressure, i.e. increase shielding at higher pressure leads to a reduced pressure derivative of the frequency shift. Again we assume that the effect of pressure on the vibrational excitation is coupled to the internuclear displacement so that there is a decrease in configuration coordinate (volume) on excitation and this corresponds to the increase in attractive solvation forces due to slight contraction of system volume. Thus, solute-solvent repulsive interaction decreases and so frequency shift deviates from linearity at appreciable pressure.

TABLE 3—SOLVENT PARAMETERS

Solvent	α_s Å ³	μ_s D	I_s cm^{-1}	$\rho_s \times 10^{-21}$ cm^{-3}	σ_s Å
CCl ₄	10.51	0	92 500	6.204 2	5.18
C ₆ H ₅ CH ₃	12.3	0.45	71 100	5.637 9	5.44
CH ₃ OH	3.32	1.70	87 500	14.786 2	3.36

The extrapolation of the curves (Fig. 1) to zero pressure (relative to one atmosphere) will give the values of frequency shifts at one atmosphere pressure. Thus our work also gives theoretical estimation of vibrational frequency shifts at one atmosphere pressure when a homonuclear diatomic gas phase solute is dissolved in a solvent, which

 Fig. 1 Pressure dependence of Cl₂ and H₂ frequency shifts in three solvents.

TABLE 4—CALCULATED VIBRATIONAL FREQUENCY SHIFTS ($n = 1$)

System	Packing fractions	Attractive component Δv_A cm^{-1}	Repulsive component Δv_R cm^{-1}	Total frequency shift Δv cm^{-1}
Chlorine-tetrachloride	0.10		3.77	-23.64
	0.20		6.70	-20.71
	0.30	-27.41	11.70	-15.71
	0.40		20.61	-6.80
	0.451 6		25.27	-2.14
Chlorine-Methanol	0.05		4.72	-33.74
	0.10		6.76	-31.70
	0.15	-38.46	9.47	-28.99
	0.20		12.82	-25.64
	0.293 7		22.84	-15.62
Chlorine-Toluene	0.10		3.53	-19.81
	0.20		7.29	-16.05
	0.30		10.84	-12.50
	0.40	-23.34	18.89	-4.45
	0.475 4		26.51	+3.17
Nitrogen-tetrachloride	0.10		0.611	-2.559
	0.20		0.868	-2.302
	0.30	-3.17	1.150	-2.02
	0.40		1.99	-1.18
	0.451 6		2.42	-0.75
Nitrogen-Methanol	0.05		0.804	-3.832
	0.10		0.973	-3.667
	0.15	-4.64	1.18	-3.46
	0.20		1.45	-3.19
	0.293 7		2.18	-2.46
Nitrogen-Toluene	0.10		0.581	-2.06
	0.20		1.05	-1.60
	0.30	-2.65	1.23	-1.42
	0.40		2.13	-0.52
	0.475 4		2.14	-0.05
Hydrogen-	0.10		3.46	-16.48

Table-4 (contd.)

Carbon	0.20		4.75	-15.19
tetrachloride	0.30	-19.94	6.77	-13.17
	0.40		12.06	-7.88
	0.451 6		12.10	-7.84
Hydrogen-	0.05		4.33	-26.86
Methanol	0.10		5.18	-26.86
	0.15	-31.19	6.13	-25.06
	0.20		7.40	-23.79
	0.293 7		10.73	-20.46
Hydrogen-	0.10		3.33	-13.10
Toluene	0.20		4.54	-11.89
	0.30		6.05	-10.38
	0.40	-16.43	9.12	-7.31
	0.475 4		12.73	-3.70

will be useful for practical means. This work can be extended to heteronuclear diatomic solutes and mixed solvent also.

The accuracy of the predicted shifts depends on the choice of hard-core diameter of the solvent as the packing force is very sensitive to the choice of solvent diameter. Variation of few percent in this diameter can cause a significant errors in the predicted frequency shifts.

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